

Preparation and Properties of Highly Concentrated Sols. Part I.

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In publications from these laboratories (Dhar and Gore, *J. Indian Chem., Soc.*, 1929, **6**, 31, 641) it has been shown that the properties of colloids depend considerably on their purity. Our experimental results obtained with sols of ferric, stannic, ceric, chromic, aluminium, zirconium and thorium hydroxides of different degrees of purity show that the viscosities of these sols increase steadily with their purity even when their concentrations are practically constant. When these hydroxide sols are very pure and unstable and when the amount of adsorbed electrolyte is very small, their viscosities are enormously increased.

On the other hand, we have shown that highly purified sols of ferric, chromic, stannic, zirconium and other hydroxides become less viscous when their electric charge and stability are increased by the addition of the peptising electrolyte. Hence it appears that the increased purity of the sols is associated with greater hydration and viscosity.

The concentrations of the pure sols investigated were not high, because when the sols are highly concentrated, they are partially or completely coagulated on attempting to purify them.

We have undertaken a systematic research with the object of preparing highly concentrated sols in as pure a condition as possible. We have also investigated the properties of these concentrated sols. In this communication we are submitting some of our results with the hydroxide sols of iron, aluminium and chromium.

Ferric Hydroxide Sol.

In order to prepare a concentrated sol of ferric hydroxide, most of the methods of preparing it were investigated. It was found that the maximum concentration of the sol obtainable by the method of adding ferric chloride solution to boiling water and subsequent

dialysis was only 18 g. of ferric oxide per litre. The concentration of the sol obtainable by the addition of ammonium carbonate solution to ferric chloride solution was not also high. It was observed that the most concentrated sol was obtained by following the method of Pean de St. Gilles. A precipitate of ferric hydroxide was obtained by adding ammonium hydroxide to a cold solution of ferric chloride. It was carefully washed, freed from chloride and peptised by a minimum quantity of acetic acid. The sol thus obtained was concentrated and purified by boiling until a small amount of precipitate was formed on the top. The sol was further purified by subjecting it to hot dialysis. The concentration of the sol was determined by evaporating a definite volume of the sol in a platinum crucible and weighing it as ferric oxide after ignition. In order to determine the purity of the sol, a definite volume of the sol was coagulated by potassium sulphate, and the ferric hydroxide particles were filtered and carefully washed, and the acetic acid in the filtrate was estimated by a standard alkali. We have always expressed the purity of a sol by the ratio Fe_2O_3 / acetic acid obtained from the same volume of the sol, both the concentrations being expressed in g. moles per litre. The following are the experimental results.

TABLE I.
Concentration and purity.

		Undialysed sol.	Dialysed sol.
Fe_2O_3 (g. per litre)	...	70.2	81
Acetic acid	..	1.97	0.96
Purity	...	13.37	31.64

TABLE II.
The Coagulation time.

Sol taken each time = 1 c.c. Total volume = 20 c.c. Time = 1 hr.

Electrolyte.	Undialysed sol		Dialysed sol	
	Amount.	Ppt. conc.	Amount.	Ppt. conc.
KCl	M/3 5.8 c.c.	0.0076 M	M/3 1.75 c.c.	0.029 M
K_2SO_4	M/30 0.855	0.0014	M/30 0.125	0.0069
$\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$	M/1200 9.9	0.0001	M/1200 5.9	0.000242
$\text{K}_1\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$	M 2800 4.1	0.00007	M/2800 2.7	0.00018

The ratio of the precipitation values of mono-, bi-, tri-, and quadrivalent ions is 1394: 20·7: 6: 1 in the case of the undialysed and 604: 14·5: 5: 1 in the case of the dialysed sol.

TABLE III.

Dialysed sol.

Sol taken each time=0·5 c.c. Total volume=20 c.c. Time=1 hr.

Electrolyte.	Amount.		Ppt. Conc.
KCl	M/3	2·58 c.c.	0·048 M
K ₂ SO ₄	M/30	0·255	0·000425
K ₃ Fe(CN) ₆	M/1200	4·1	0·00017
K ₄ Fe(CN) ₆	M/2800	1·9	8·000033

TABLE IV.

Viscosity.

Conc. (Sol)	Viscosity of undialysed sol.	Density of undialysed sol.	Viscosity of dialysed sol.	Density of dialysed sol.
Sol A (original)	4·8	1·067	2036	1·070
Sol A/2	23·8	1·050
Sol A/4	5·2	1·032
Sol A/8	2·15	1·020
Sol A/16	1·37	1·008
Water	1·00	

The viscosity of the dialysed sol at first changes with time and then becomes constant. The viscosity results recorded are those obtained when the viscosities become constant. In the case of sol A/2 the time taken for the flow of 7 c.c. of sol decreased from 1 min. 18 sec. to 1 min. 8 sec. and the time taken for the same volume of water is 3 sec. only and for sol A/4, the time of fall decreased from 8 min. 30 sec. to 7 min. 57·5 sec., the time taken for the same volume of water being 1 min. 35 sec. The viscosity was determined at 20° by an Ostwald viscometer. In the case of the highly concentrated sols the diameter of the capillary tube used was much greater than that of the tube used for the less concentrated sols.

Aluminium Hydroxide Sol.

In preparing a concentrated sol of aluminium hydroxide, the freshly precipitated and well washed aluminium hydroxide was peptised by the minimum quantity of acetic acid. It was slightly warmed on a water-bath until the sol was clear. This was then subjected to hot dialysis. The concentration and purity were determined as in the case of ferric hydroxide sol.

TABLE V.
Concentration and purity.

		Undialysed sol.	Dialysed sol.
Al ₂ O ₃ (g. per litre)	...	53.6	38.4
Acetic acid	..	26.42	17.4
Purity	...	1.193	1.298

TABLE VI.
Coagulation.

Sol taken each time=0.5 c.c. Total volume=10 c.c. Time=1 hr.

Electrolyte.	Undialysed.		Dialysed.	
	Amount.	Ppt. conc.	Amount.	Ppt. conc.
KCl	3.47M 4.1 c.c.	1.42 M	3.47 M 1.5 c.c.	0.5205 M
K ₂ SO ₄	M/30 1.7	0.0056	M/30 0.55	0.0018
K ₃ Fe(CN) ₆	M/150 3.7	0.0025	M/150 1.3	0.00086
K ₄ Fe(CN) ₆	M/240 4.7	0.0019	M/240 1.7	0.0007

Ratio of the precipitating values of the above four electrolytes in molar concentration is 747:2.94:1.3:1 with undialysed sol and 743.5:2.5:1.2:1 with dialysed sol.

TABLE VII.

Sol taken each time=0.25 c.c. Total volume=10 c.c. Time=1hr.

Electrolyte.	Amount.	Ppt. conc.
KCl	3.47 M 1.9 c.c.	0.6593
K ₂ SO ₄	M/30 0.35	0.00116
K ₃ Fe(CN) ₆	M/150 0.6	0.00042
K ₄ Fe(CN) ₆	M/240 0.85	0.00035

TABLE VIII.

Viscosity.

Conc. (Sol)	Viscosity of undialysed sol.	Density of undialysed sol.	Viscosity of dialysed sol.	Density of dialysed sol.
Sol A	7.31	1.058	98.1	1.03
A/2	2.427	1.020	8.72	1.01
A/4	1.587	1.012	2.54	1.004
A/8	1.262	1.002	1.52	...
A/16	1.103	...	1.25	...

With the concentrated sols of aluminium hydroxide, at first the viscosity changes with time and then becomes constant.

Chromic Hydroxide Sol.

As in the case of the other two, peptisation with acetic acid was tried but it did not give satisfactory result, because when the sol was subjected to hot dialysis even in a collodion bag, hardly anything was left in the bag.

Another method was adopted in which a concentrated solution of chromic chloride was boiled and ammonium carbonate solution was added gradually till a slight amount of precipitate formed. It was then subjected to continuous hot dialysis, the temperature being kept at 70°-80°.

TABLE IX.

Concentration and purity.

		Dialysed for 3 hrs.	Dialysed for 22 hrs.
Cr ₂ O ₃ (g. per litre)	...	109	127
Cl	"	32.8	19.8
Purity	...	0.774	1.496

TABLE X.

Coagulation.

Sol taken = 0.5 c.c. Total volume = 20 c.c. Time = 1 hr.

Electrolyte.	Dialysed sol I.		Dialysed sol II.	
	Amount.	Ppt. conc.	Amount.	Ppt. conc.
KIO ₃	M/3 0.75 c.c.	0.0125 M	M/3 0.45 c.c.	0.0075 M
K ₂ SO ₄	M/30 5.3	0.0088	M/30 3.3	0.0055
K ₃ Fe(CN) ₆	M/60 5.75	0.0048	M/60 4.5	0.0037
K ₄ Fe(CN) ₆	M/80 3.5	0.0022	M/80 3.0	0.0018

Ratios of the precipitation values in molar concentration are 5.7 : 4.2 : 18 : 1 for dialysed sol I (for 3 hours) and 4.16 : 3.05 : 2.05 : 1 for dialysed sol II (for 22 hours).

TABLE XI.
 ○
 Dialysed sol II.

Sol taken = 0.5 c.c. Total volume = 20 c.c. Time = 1 hr.

Electrolyte.	Amount.	Ppt. conc.
KIO ₃	M/3 0.25 c.c.	0.0041
K ₂ SO ₄	M/30 1.7	0.0528
K ₃ Fe(CN) ₆	M/60 2.3	0.0019

TABLE XII.

Viscosity.

Conc.	Viscosity of dialysed sol I.	Density of dialysed sol I.	Viscosity of dialysed sol II.	Density of dialysed sol II.
Sol A	2.19	1.210	1643	1.300
A/2	1.41	1.067	21.95	1.120
A/4	1.24	1.037	5.3	1.031
A/8	1.10	1.014	2.2	...
A/16	1.04	...	1.47	...

The viscosity of concentrated sols of chromium hydroxide also changes with time in the beginning and then becomes constant.

Surface Tension.

Since the lowering of surface tension has been generally considered as typical of the lyophilic colloids, attempts have been made to determine the surface tension of these hydroxide sols with a Traube stalagmometer. As the sols were highly viscous, the time required for the formation of each drop was considerable. Due to the evaporation from the drop surface during the formation of drops, these results appear to be only comparative.

TABLE XIII.

Sol.	Density of the sols.	Surface tension of sols.	Surface tension of water.
Fe(OH) ₃	1·070	72·1	72·45
Cr(OH) ₃	1·301	72·0	72·24
Al(OH) ₃	1·031	67·1	72·94

There is only slight decrease in surface tension from that of water in the case of ferric and chromic hydroxide sols but with aluminium hydroxide sol, the fall in surface tension is quite marked. Further work is in progress.

Discussion.

From the experimental results it will be seen that we have been able to obtain highly concentrated sols of the hydroxides of iron, aluminium and chromium. The concentrations of the sols so far are as follows :

TABLE XIV

		g. per litre.
Ferric hydroxide (dialysed)	...	81 (Fe ₂ O ₃)
Aluminium hydroxide (undialysed)	...	53·6 (Al ₂ O ₃)
Chromic hydroxide (dialysed)	...	127 (Cr ₂ O ₃)

It will be interesting to note that the most concentrated sol of ferric hydroxide, that was prepared before our work, contained only 35 g. of Fe₂O₃ per litre (Geffcken, *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1904, **49**, 297).

On comparing the precipitating concentrations of electrolytes for the undialysed and dialysed sols of Fe(OH)₃, Al(OH)₃, and Cr(OH)₃ it will be seen that the values in the case of the dialysed sols are less than those for the undialysed ones. Because with dialysis, the stabilising electrolytes are removed and thus the charge on the colloid decreases. In other words, the sol becomes more sensitive towards electrolytes. (Dhar and Gore, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, **6**, 31). Moreover it will be seen, that the ratio of the amounts of monovalent and bivalent electrolytes necessary to coagulate the sols falls off considerably on dialysis and these results are in agreement with those previously obtained by Dhar and Gore.

Influence of Concentration on the Coagulation of the Sols.

In several publications from these laboratories it has been shown that the amount of uni-univalent electrolytes, necessary for coagulation of the sols of ferric, chromic and aluminium hydroxides is greater, the greater the concentration of the sol, when the sol is coagulated by electrolytes like KCl, KIO_3 and KBrO_3 . Moreover, it was also shown that when these hydroxide sols contain appreciable amount of acids, the stability of the sol is greatly increased and increasing amounts of uni-univalent electrolytes are required for coagulation of the sol when it is diluted continuously.

It is evident from the foregoing pages that the sols studied in this paper contain acids. Appreciable amount of acetic acid is associated with the sols of ferric and aluminium hydroxides. The chromic hydroxide sol was acidic due to the presence of hydrochloric acid, so it could not be coagulated by potassium chloride. Consequently it is expected that these sols should behave abnormally towards dilution when coagulated by uni-univalent electrolytes. Our experimental results show also that the amount of KCl required to coagulate the diluted sol is greater than that required to coagulate the concentrated one. The degree of dissociation of acetic acid, which is associated with the sols increases with dilution and the amount of H ion adsorbed is more marked with the diluted than with the concentrated ones. Consequently the stability and the charge on the colloid are greater in the diluted condition than in the concentrated one.

From the results on the coagulation of chromium hydroxide sol, it will be seen that KIO_3 exerts practically the same influence as K_2SO_4 . Similar results have been obtained by Weiser and Middleton (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1920, **24**, 30). It has recently been emphasised by Dhar (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, **5**, 58) that iodic acid and iodates contain in solution the bivalent ion $\text{I}_2\text{O}_6''$ and that is why the coagulating power of the iodate ion is practically the same as that of the sulphate ion.

It appears that the iodate ions have marked chemical affinity for the hydroxides of iron, aluminium and chromium, because the adsorption of iodate ions is greater than that of Cl' or SO_4'' ions, under identical conditions. It has been emphasised in several publications from these laboratories that the amount of adsorption of an ion by a sol is not only controlled by the amount of the electric charge on the sol, but the chemical affinity of the uncharged particles for the ions, also plays an important part.

Viscosity.

The influence of electric charge on the viscosity of colloids has been considered by several investigators. Wo. Ostwald recognises the influence of electric charge on the viscosity of colloids in the following terms—'Every electrically charged particle induces about it an electromagnetic field which hinders its movements whether such is spontaneous or brought from without. Hardy (*Z. Phys. Chem.* 1900, 33, 398) observed the generation of a cataphoretic current from the fall of electrically charged particles. Smoluchowski (*Kolloid Z.*, 1916, 18, 194) concluded that the movements of electrically charged particles of a sol causes the development of an electrical field, which hinders the flow of the sol resulting in the increment of the viscosity. Smoluchowski reported that a sol with greater electric charge shows greater viscosity than a sol containing particles of feeble electric charge. Krut and his coworkers (*Koll. Chem. Beih.*, 1929, 28, 1; 1929, 29, 413) are also of opinion that an increase in electric charge on a sol produces an increment in its viscosity.

Dhar and his collaborators have, however, shown from experimental results with no less than 30 sols that the views of Ostwald, Smoluchowski, and Krut are untenable. Dhar concludes that other things being identical, a decrease in the electric charge on colloid particles causes an increase in hydration and necessarily in the viscosity of the sol. The viscosity measurements with the undialysed and dialysed sols of ferric, aluminium and chromic hydroxides show that the viscosities with a sol of feeble charge are remarkably high in comparison with that of a sol of high electric charge. These experimental results are in agreement with the views of Dhar. In measuring the viscosity of the hydroxide sols, we have observed that the time of fall through the capillary gradually decreased until a constant value is reached. Similar results showing a decrease in viscosity with increase in the shearing force with lyophilic sols like gelatin and starch were obtained by Hatschek (*Kolloid Z.* 1913, 13, 88). It seems probable that with repeated forcing of the highly hydrated and viscous sols through the capillary, the hydrated colloid particles are subjected to a shearing force with consequent loss of adsorbed water up to a limiting value. Banerji and Ghosh (private communication) however, ascribe this decrease of viscosity to the disturbance in the structure of the highly viscous sol.

The viscosity concentration curve has been plotted with these hydroxide sols and they are found to be very steep and logarithmic in nature. These curves are of the same nature as those obtained with typical lyophilic sols like gelatin, agar and starch. It appears, therefore, that as far as viscosity is concerned the highly concentrated sols of iron, aluminium and chromium behave like lyophilic colloids.

Arrhenius (*Medd. K. Vetensk.*, 1916, 3, no. 13) has deduced the empirical formula for the viscosity concentration relation for lyophilic sols as $\log \eta = \theta c$, where η = relative viscosity of the dispersed phase, θ = constant, and c = molecular concentration of the sol. The Arrhenius equation applies very well to our results obtained with the hydroxide sols. When the logarithm of the viscosities are plotted against the concentrations, a straight line is obtained.

In order to calculate the amount of hydration, the equations of Hatschek and Arrhenius have been utilised. The formula suggested

by Hatschek (*Kolloid-Z.*, 1911, 8, 34) is $\eta_s = \frac{\eta_o}{1 - \sqrt{\phi}}$ where η_s and

η_o are the viscosities of the sol and dispersion medium respectively and ϕ = effective volume of the colloid particles. The hydration factor can be calculated from the observed viscosities and from the known weight concentration ϕ' by applying the above relation of Hatschek in the following form:

$h\phi' = \left(\frac{\eta_s - \eta_o}{\eta_s} \right)^3$; h is the hydration factor by which the weight concentration must be multiplied to give the volume concentration (effective volume) which enters into the formula, i.e., $h\phi' = \phi$.

Hatschek emphasises that if this formula be applied to typical emulsoid sols of proteins, the constancy of h is maintained over a moderate range of concentrations. But the factor ϕ/ϕ' with the hydroxide sols does not show any constancy. Arrhenius (*Medd. K. Vetensk.*, 1916, 3, no. 13) deduced that for substances with very high molecular weight, the molecular concentration is given by the relation

$C = \theta \frac{100p}{100 - (n+1)p}$ where θ = constant, p = weight of the dry substance

in 100 c.c. of sol, n = hydration factor, i.e., number of grams of solvent associated with one gram of solute. He obtained constant values of n in the case of protein sols. On calculating the value of n with our sols, we find the values to be negative.

It is apparent, therefore, that the exact determination of hydration from the viscosity measurement is not possible. It may be of interest to point out here that the degree of hydration for ions as obtained by different authors by various methods, does not agree and the values are looked upon with considerable uncertainty. Hence it is not surprising that the measurement of the degree of hydration for a colloid particle, which does not represent a stable state of existence, is based on still more uncertain factors. It should, however, be borne in mind that the measurement of viscosity (though not reliable in giving us a correct value for the degree of hydration) certainly conveys a qualitative idea of the hydration of colloid particles.

Reversibility of the Sols.

A curious phenomenon has been observed in the case of these hydroxide sols. The viscous sols can be dried in air and the dry mass can be reprecipitated by cold water. Uptil now this reversibility has only been observed in the case of the typical lyophilic sols, namely gelatin, agar etc. This reversibility is most prominent with $\text{Cr}(\text{OH})_3$ sol and least in the $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ sol. When the solid dry hydroxides are placed in water, they gradually swell, become transparent and finally pass into a clear colloidal solution. Warming hinders this process. Ferric hydroxide sol when completely dried in air becomes irreversible and is not reprecipitated when put into water. The dry reversible solids have been analysed and the results are as follows:

TABLE XV.

Air dried chromium hydroxide sol.

Constituents	Percentage composition.
Cr_2O_3	44.18
Cl'	13.1
Water	42.8

TABLE XVI.

Air dried aluminium hydroxide sol.

Constituents	Percentage composition.
Al_2O_3	55.2
Acetate	1.01
Water	44

The empirical formula derived for the dried chromic hydroxide sol from the percentage composition is $\text{Cr}_5(\text{OH})_{11}\text{Cl}_3, 28\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Bjerrum (*Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1910, 73, 724) claimed to have obtained the basic salts $\text{Cr}(\text{OH})_2\text{Cl}$ and $\text{Cr}(\text{OH})\text{Cl}_2$. The basic compound

$\text{Cr}_2(\text{OH})_{12}\text{Cl}_3 \cdot 28\text{H}_2\text{O}$ obtained by us is not mentioned in the literature. Moreover by splitting the formula in the form $[\text{Cr}(\text{OH})_3 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}]_4\text{CrCl}_3$ it is clear that one molecule of chromic chloride is associated with 4 molecules of $\text{Cr}(\text{OH})_3$ and each molecule of $\text{Cr}(\text{OH})_3$ is associated with 7 molecules of water of hydration. When viewed with a high power microscope, the dry substance appears to consist of regular layers of solid. The empirical formula of the dried aluminium hydroxide is $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O} \cdot \text{CH}_3\text{COOH}$. The dried mass of the aluminium compound is transparent and looks like glass.

In this connection it is to be noted that a high degree of hydration is not associated with the reversibility of the hydroxide sols. From our results, it will be seen that ferric hydroxide sol is more viscous than the other two at more or less the same concentration, but the property of reversibility is least developed with ferric hydroxide sol. Whilst the chromic hydroxide sol, though the least viscous and consequently the least hydrated of the three, is the most easily reversible. Kruyt and his coworkers (*Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1922, **100**, 250) have shown that hydration is closely associated with the stability of the sols towards their coagulation by electrolytes. According to these investigators, layers of water envelop the colloid particles and protect them from agglomeration on neutralisation of electric charge. Ghosh and Dhar (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1930, **34**, 326) have shown that this view of Kruyt supported by Freundlich (*Koll. Chem. Beih.*, 1922, **16**, 234) is untenable in view of their experimental results on the coagulation of highly viscous and hydrated inorganic sols. Our results on the coagulation of these hydroxide sols also point to the fact that the conclusion of Kruyt and Freundlich and others are not justified. Thus ferric hydroxide sol has been found in these investigations to be highly hydrated, whilst the sol is the least stable of three hydroxides investigated in this paper. It seems on the other hand that the stability of a sol towards the action of electrolytes is more related with the electric charge on the colloid particles than with its hydration. Chromic hydroxide sol, which contains a large amount of chromic chloride, is necessarily less viscous and hydrated because of the comparatively high electric charge on the particles and is most stable amongst these three hydroxide sols. We are of opinion that high viscosity and hence greater hydration are not necessarily a cause of stability of the sols towards their coagulation.

Summary.

1. Highly concentrated sols of ferric, chromic and aluminium hydroxides have been prepared. The concentrations being 81 g. (0.5063 gram mole) Fe_2O_3 per litre, 53.6 g. (0.5255 gram mole) Al_2O_3 per litre and 127 g. (0.8356 gram mole) Cr_2O_3 per litre.

2. These hydroxide sols of iron, aluminium and chromium could not be completely freed from the peptising substances even by hot dialysis. It has been found that if the dialysis be carried beyond the purity mentioned, the hydroxides set to firm jellies.

3. The undialysed sol of the same concentration is more stable towards electrolytes than the dialysed ones. The ratio of the precipitating concentrations of uni- to bivalent ions decreases as the purity of the sol increases.

4. The viscosity of the sols is exceedingly high in the concentrated condition and increases with purity even their when concentrations are practically identical. The results of viscosity measurements show that the less the charge on a colloid, the greater is its viscosity. These results are in agreement with the views of Dhar that the viscosity of a colloid increases as the charge decreases.

5. The viscosity concentration curves with these hydroxide sols are very steep and resemble those obtained with typically lyophilic sols.

6. Preliminary measurements of surface tension show that the values of the surface tension of ferric and chromic hydroxide sols are slightly less than that of water but in the case of aluminium hydroxide, the fall in surface tension is quite marked.

7. The highly concentrated sols of aluminium and chromium hydroxide behave as reversible colloids in as much as the air dried solids obtained from these sols swell and again pass into colloidal condition when kept in contact with water.

